

Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form

Participant Information Sheet

Study Title: Regulatory Frameworks and Practices for Wastewater Reuse in Agricultural Irrigation

Research Project: SYMSITES – Sustainable Management of Symbiotic Industrial Wastewater Systems

Principal Investigators: [Names and affiliations]

Purpose of the Study:

The purpose of this study is to explore regulatory frameworks and practices governing the reuse of wastewater in agricultural irrigation in selected European Union countries (Spain, Greece, Austria, Denmark) and non-EU countries (Israel, United States, Indonesia). The study aims to identify best practices, barriers to implementation, and recommendations for policymakers.

What Participation Involves:

- You will take part in a semi-structured interview lasting approximately 30–60 minutes.
- The interview will be audio-recorded with your permission.
- You may decline to answer any question and may withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason.

Voluntary Participation and Right to Withdraw:

Participation is voluntary. You may choose to stop the interview at any time. If you withdraw, any data you have provided will not be used in the analysis.

Risks and Benefits:

There are no known risks associated with participating in this study. While there are no direct benefits to you, your participation will help improve understanding of wastewater reuse policies and practices.

Confidentiality and Data Protection:

- Your identity will be kept confidential. We will not record your name or any identifiable personal information in the transcripts.
- Audio recordings will be securely stored and destroyed after transcription and anonymization.
- Anonymized transcripts and data will be made publicly available under a Creative Commons license for research and educational purposes.

Use of Data:

Anonymized transcripts may be used for academic publications and presentations. Data will be stored in a public repository (e.g. Zenodo) under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0) license.

Contact Information:

If you have questions about the study, please contact [Researcher's name and contact information]. If you have concerns about your rights as a participant, please contact [Ethics Board contact information].

Consent Form

I have read the information provided above and understand the purpose of this study. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study, and my questions have been answered. I understand that I may withdraw at any time without penalty. I consent to the interview being audio-recorded.

- **Participant's Signature:** _____
- **Printed Name:** _____
- **Date:** _____
- **Researcher's Signature:** _____
- **Printed Name:** _____
- **Date:** _____